

TOPONYMY AND LINGUISTICS.

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***Annotation:** Toponymy is the science that has its subject the study of geographical names or toponyms. As all other names, toponyms belong to languages. Whether they carry a physical meaning in all cases they once used the vocabulary and followed the grammatical and orthographic rules of a certain language. In this article some relations between language and toponyms are mentioned.*

***Key terms:** toponymy, linguistics, standards, applied toponymy, the name-giver, semantic and morphologic units, conglomerate, toponymic importance, toponymic sense, linguistic status.*

Names in general are only rarely randomly chosen, and this is especially true in the case of geographical names. Whether they carry a physical meaning or they were coined to honour someone, to commemorate some historic event or to make clear to whom the named object belonged, in all cases they once used the vocabulary and followed the grammatical and orthographic rules of a certain language. Languages are the subjects of the science called linguistics. Therefore, anyone handling geographical names needs to have some basic linguistic knowledge, both in general terms and specifically pertaining to the language situation of the area of survey. People usually start looking for the meaning of names that are incomprehensible to them and try to pronounce by adapting them to their own language, more precisely false etymology, appears in this way, and thus legends are also made up.

People from different professional backgrounds may be allured to some kind of study of geographical names. To linguists specializing either in the historical or genealogical aspects of specific languages, or in the taxonomy of languages in general, toponyms contain a treasure of ancient language elements which allows them to under build their theories or test their hypotheses. Likewise, historians may use toponym research to reveal ancient movements of peoples, or get a hint of cultural exchange patterns in forgotten ages. Moreover, recurrent name elements are known to store information on the history of settlement and land reclamation, the economic activities of the original settlers, and political developments. Topographers and cartographers often bear a less theoretical interest in toponymy: they simply need to know by what names every object to be mapped has to be known and recorded. As far as the last mentioned category of professionals does not study geographical names for the sake of the names themselves, but rather wants to constitute a set of rules, or standards, defining what should be considered ‘right’ and ‘wrong’ in the cartographic naming practice, they are involved in what we call applied toponymy. Even if exhaustive linguistic knowledge is not required to be able to practise this specific kind of applied toponymy, a basic understanding of the linguistic and historic context of the geographical names within the area of study is certainly indispensable.

At the moment a name is given to an object, the language of the name-giver provides both the elements needed and the structure to join them together. The elements consist of semantic and morphologic units – units of meaning and form - called words and morphemes. The former are the smallest units that may occur independently, the latter the even smaller particles, like suffixes and affixes forming part of or joined to them. The structure is provided in the form of a set of rules called grammar, that defines the way the language can be used to convey (communicate) meaning. An important constituent of grammar is the syntax, determining the way

words should be linked together into larger semantic conglomerates. Most names start their existence as such a semantic conglomerate.

The linguistic abracadabra above may easily be clarified by picking the first name that comes to mind, for instance: Stratford-upon-Avon. This English town that became world famous thanks to the birth of William Shakespeare clearly consists of three elements, which are, obviously in accordance with some syntactic rule specifically applying to English names, separated by hyphens. Two of the elements start with a capital, the one in the middle doesn't: again a syntactic rule. As a capital initial letter is commonly used in (Roman) written language to denote that a word is either the beginning of a sentence or a name, we get the idea that both 'Stratford' and 'Avon' are names in themselves, and 'upon' is not. We need to know that 'upon' is a preposition, meant to establish a situational link between 'Stratford' and 'Avon'. Both of the remaining elements of this name also enclose a meaning for themselves, that at the time of the name-giving must have been considered important: this meaning had to ensure that upon mentioning it would make clear which geographical object was meant, without anyone needing to point at it.

Toponymic importance of individual languages from a global point of view, obviously not all language families are as important, as far as numbers measure importance. More than 75% of all languages belong to only 10 of the 100 recognized families, while judged by the numbers of speakers, two-thirds of the world population speak languages belonging to only two families (Indo-European and Sino-Tibetan). To the topographic-cartographic toponymist, however, other numbers may be even more relevant: after all, the number of geographic names to be dealt with is not so much dependent on current numbers of speakers, as it is on the geographic extent of the area to be surveyed and the scale of mapping the survey is carried out for. Topographic map series of a certain scale use to cover a complete country, irrespective of differences in population density.

To further illustrate the complexity of defining the importance of a language to toponymy, let us stick to the Siberian Nenets a little longer. Especially during the last century, the Nenets homeland has received an influx of Russian settlers, who soon outnumbered the Nenets in their own provinces – be it that the newcomers settled in just a few urban settlements. Furthermore, from the 1950-s on the Soviet authorities were rather successful in putting the nomadic lifestyle of the Nenets to an end. But the many streams, lakes and other physical landscape elements had for long been named by them. And most of them had been named only once: by the Nenets. By the nature of their nomadic lifestyle, in contrary to that of the new urban settlers, to them little in the landscape was without meaning and therefore without the need of a name.

Two other issues have to be taken into account when evaluating the relationship between numbers of speakers and the importance of a language from a toponymic point of view. One involves the level of geographic (or regional) attachment of a language, the other the ‘historic rights’ the speakers of a language enjoy to the land where they settled. Both can be easily illustrated reviewing the situation in one of the most stable countries we can think of.

Just like in the context of toponymy numbers of speakers do have another weight than they have from a general linguistic point of view, the question whether or not a language is being officially recognized as such also has less importance in a toponymic sense. This so-called question of linguistic status – is a specific system of common speech to be considered a real ‘independent’ language, or, alternatively, ‘just a dialect’ of a ‘real’ language? – is answered differently depending on the considerations of who is asked. Political considerations in this may prove to be dominant above any linguistic criteria.

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